

Network Slicing and Edge-Driven UAV Surveillance in 5G Private Networks for Industrial Digital Transformation in the Aerospace Sector

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Abstract—This paper presents a 5G-enabled private network solution designed to support industrial digital transformation within the aerospace sector. Building upon prior research that identified 5G adoption challenges in the Ayrshire region of Scotland, this work introduces a practical use case demonstrating an integrated 5G and edge computing system for autonomous aerial surveillance. The proposed system employs a 5G private network with network slicing to guarantee ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) even under network congestion. A fleet of 5G-enabled Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) form a resilient mesh network using the Better Approach To Mobile Adhoc Networking (BATMAN) protocol to maintain continuous connectivity. At the network edge, a Human Detector AI module performs real-time intruder detection using a custom deep learning model, UWS-YOLO. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that network slicing ensures service continuity for mission-critical applications, highlighting the potential of 5G MPNs as a key enabler of digital transformation for the aerospace sector and the wider industrial landscape.

Index Terms—5G, Private Networks, Edge Computing, Network Slicing, BATMAN, UAV, Drone Surveillance, YOLO, URLLC, Aerospace, Digital Transformation

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation (5G) of mobile communication systems represents a transformative step toward enabling ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), massive machine-type communication (mMTC), and enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB). Despite these promises, industrial 5G adoption in Scotland remains uneven, as highlighted in previous works assessing 5G adoption challenges in the Ayrshire region [1]. The findings revealed key barriers: awareness gaps, cost concerns, and uncertainty surrounding 5G-exclusive capabilities that hinder uptake across both public and private sectors.

This work builds upon that foundation by demonstrating a 5G-enabled UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) surveillance system—hereafter referred to as *drones*—integrated with a private 5G network and edge computing for aerospace facility and control. The proposed system leverages a 5G Mobile Private Network (MPN) to support optimal Quality of Ser-

vice (QoS) low-latency video transmission, a BATMAN-ADV-based UAV mesh network for resilient connectivity, and an edge AI module for real-time intruder detection. The aim is to demonstrate the suitability of 5G when supporting complex use cases with stringent latency and throughput requirements, showcasing measurable reliability and operational value of 5G-enabled solutions for industrial environments [2].

Beyond demonstrating technological feasibility, this work highlights the potential benefits of 5G-based surveillance over traditional wired and Wi-Fi systems. Conventional surveillance infrastructures often suffer from fixed camera positioning, limited coverage, and high cabling costs, while Wi-Fi-based solutions face bandwidth saturation, interference, and weak security protocols. In contrast, a 5G Private Networks enable flexible and scalable surveillance through mobile UAVs capable of covering large or remote industrial sites without the need for additional cabling. Moreover, 5G offers enhanced encryption and network isolation compared with Wi-Fi, ensuring greater data security and reliability for mission-critical operations. This convergence of mobility, low latency, and security positions 5G-driven UAV systems as a compelling enabler for next-generation industrial monitoring and digital transformation.

The contributions of this paper are threefold:

- 1) The design and deployment of a 5G-enabled UAV surveillance architecture for aerospace operations.
- 2) The integration of BATMAN-based mesh networking and network slicing to achieve seamless and resilient connectivity.
- 3) The experimental validation of real-time edge-based human detection under varying network conditions.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The deployment of 5G mobile communication systems has been widely recognised as a catalyst for digital transformation across industrial sectors. However, our previous study on 5G adoption in the Ayrshire region of Scotland revealed that

the industrial uptake of 5G remains limited and fragmented. Our findings underscore a persistent gap between theoretical understanding and real-world implementation. Consequently, there is a pressing need for domain-specific demonstrators that translate 5G's advanced features—low latency, reliability, and programmability—into tangible industrial benefits. This work directly addresses that need by presenting a practical 5G Private Network implementation within an aerospace operational context, showcasing its technical and economic potential [3].

A. Private 5G Networks as Enablers of Industrial Transformation

Private 5G networks are emerging as a cornerstone of modern Industrial automation and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIOT), providing enterprises with full control of network resources, data sovereignty, and performance optimisation. Unlike public cellular infrastructure, a Private 5G Network enables localised, deterministic control of latency, bandwidth, and security policies—capabilities critical for mission-critical applications such as predictive maintenance, robotics, and industrial monitoring [4]. The disaggregated architecture of 5G, particularly within the Open RAN (O-RAN) paradigm, facilitates modular experimentation through virtualised and cloud-native components, allowing seamless integration of edge computing and AI services.

In the aerospace sector, the developing needs of operations such as aircraft inspection, facility surveillance, and training often require reliable real-time connectivity across large and complex sites [5]. Traditional surveillance systems—comprising fixed wired cameras or Wi-Fi-based wireless cameras—face significant limitations. Wired infrastructures are costly to deploy and inflexible to reconfigure, while Wi-Fi networks suffer from limited coverage, interference, and weaker security guarantees [6].

By contrast, 5G Private Networks offer deterministic Quality-of-Service (QoS) provisioning, extended range, and enhanced encryption mechanisms. Combined with edge computing, they enable data to be processed close to the source, significantly reducing response times for time-critical analytics. Network slicing further allows the prioritisation of critical services—such as real-time video transmission—over less urgent traffic, ensuring service continuity even under heavy network load.

This use case serves a dual purpose. Technically, it demonstrates the ability of 5G private networks to sustain ultra-reliable connectivity and edge-driven analytics in real-world industrial conditions. Strategically, it provides empirical evidence to stakeholders (regional policymakers, enterprises, and technology providers) of how private 5G infrastructure can act as a catalyst for digital transformation across the wider industrial landscape.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND USE CASE DESIGN

A. Overview of the Aerospace Scenario

The proposed use case emulates an operational aerospace test facility composed of three functional

zones—Hangars A, B, and C—each representing a different class of industrial activity interconnected through the 5G Private Network, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The scenario is designed to assess the capabilities of the private 5G network under concurrent service demands such as immersive training and real-time surveillance.

- **Hangar A – AR/VR Training Zone:** This zone hosts an augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) training system for maintenance personnel. The application relies on high-throughput and low-latency 5G connectivity to stream real-time content to AR headsets. It operates over an enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) slice, ensuring stable performance for immersive multimedia delivery.
- **Hangars B and C – Secure Facilities:** These zones represent restricted-access areas equipped with autonomous UAVs responsible for perimeter surveillance and intrusion detection. Each UAV is fitted with a high-definition camera and with Wi-Fi interfaces to support a mesh configuration using the BATMAN-ADV protocol.

During normal operation, Drone 1 (D1) remains within the primary 5G coverage area and serves as a network bridge between the private 5G infrastructure and the UAV mesh. Drones 2 (D2) and 3 (D3) extend surveillance coverage to remote hangar zones by relaying their video feeds through D1 via Wi-Fi-based multi-hop communication. When an intrusion event is detected, the drones automatically establish a mesh topology that adapts to environmental changes and link quality. Video streams from D2 and D3 are aggregated at D1 and transmitted via the 5G uplink to the edge computing system, where real-time analytics are performed.

The 5G Private Network employs network slicing to differentiate and prioritise service classes: a URLLC-configured slice for UAV video transmission, an eMBB slice for AR/VR applications, and a best-effort slice for background traffic and telemetry. This configuration enables the testbed to evaluate how slice allocation can maintain service continuity and latency guarantees even during network congestion.

B. 5G Private Network Infrastructure

The 5G private network used in this scenario integrates radio and computing infrastructure within the DCIC testbed, built on BubbleRAN's MX-PDK O-RAN platform with distributed and centralised units connected to a standalone 5G Core. Local edge computing nodes are co-located with the radio units to minimise round-trip latency, while Raspberry Pi devices with 5G modems serve as user equipment for both UAV connectivity and synthetic traffic generation. The system integrates real-time monitoring for throughput and latency, enabling end-to-end evaluation of how the 5G private network supports differentiated services through slicing and edge processing in an aerospace context.

C. BATMAN-ADV-based MESH Network

To ensure robust and decentralized communication among drones, a wireless MESH network was implemented using the

ensuring that detection events can be consumed simultaneously by multiple downstream services.

Persistent storage of detection data is handled by a MongoDB database, which records both raw detection events and associated UAV telemetry. This configuration enables post-mission analysis, replay of detection sequences, and the evaluation of mission performance metrics such as detection frequency and false-positive rate.

The entire edge processing pipeline (MediaMTX, the Human Detector AI, RabbitMQ, and MongoDB) is orchestrated as a set of interdependent Kubernetes pods, each described via a Helm chart. This design ensures fault isolation, automated restarts, and horizontal scalability, allowing the system to dynamically allocate additional inference modules when multiple UAVs are active.

F. Network Slicing and QoS Management

Dedicated slices are configured for each service type:

- **URLLC Slice:** For drone video analytics.
- **eMBB Slice:** For AR training and streaming.
- **Best-Effort Slice:** For background traffic.

An xApp-based control system enforces slicing and QoS guarantees dynamically.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND IMPLEMENTATION

The experimental validation was conducted using the Digital Connectivity and Innovation Centre's (DCIC) 5G Private Network testbed, located at the University of the West of Scotland. The testbed is based on a cloud-native O-RAN architecture enabling flexible experimentation with slicing, edge intelligence, and heterogeneous device integration [9].

A. Network Architecture

DCIC's O-RAN deployment is based on BubbleRAN's MX-PDK platform, offering a cloud-native, disaggregated RAN architecture. It supports independent Radio Units (RUs), Distributed Units (DUs), and Central Units (CUs) connected via O-RAN 7.2 interfaces. The platform leverages virtualisation and edge computing to facilitate research, innovation, and experimental deployments.

1) *Core and RAN Configuration:* The testbed operates in standalone (SA) mode, ensuring full 5G core functionality including user plane separation, network slicing, and QoS enforcement. The BubbleRAN MX-PDK provides a flexible management plane through a RESTful API and xApp-based control layer. Edge computing resources are co-located with the DU/CU cluster to minimise round-trip delay between radio and compute domains.

2) *Equipment Selection and Integration:* Key components include:

- **MX-PDK Compute Nodes (x3):** High-performance workstations with 25 Gbps network interfaces running the virtualised CU/DU functions.
- **Lite-On FlexiFI O-RU n78 (x2):** Indoor 4x4 MIMO radio units operating at 3.7–3.8 GHz with 100 MHz bandwidth.

- **FibroLAN Falcon-RX Switch + GNSS:** Provides IEEE 1588 PTP-based time synchronisation for the DUs via time-aware networking.
- **Quectel RM500 5G Modules (x5):** Integrated into Raspberry Pi 5 devices for user equipment (UE) simulation.
- **Software Stack:** OpenAirInterface (OAI) for 5G NR protocol stack, FlexRIC for xApp integration, ODIN orchestration, Kubernetes, Docker, Grafana, and Timescale DB for telemetry and monitoring.

and are assembled as shown in Fig 3.

B. Edge and Device Layer Integration

The end-to-end experimental environment consists of a hybrid system integrating drones, edge computing nodes, and IoT endpoints operating over the 5G Private Network.

1) *Raspberry Pi and UE Configuration:* Each Raspberry Pi 5 device runs Ubuntu 22.04 with an attached Quectel RM500 module and DCIC-issued 5G SIM. The Raspberry Pis serve multiple roles: AR/VR training simulation, traffic generation, and drone control. Network telemetry and latency monitoring agents are containerised using Docker.

2) *Drone and Camera Subsystem:* Three drones are deployed in the test scenario shown:

- **Drone 1 (D1):** Equipped with a 5G UE and acts as a mobile network extender. It serves as a gateway for the Wi-Fi mesh network, enabling wider network connectivity for peer drones.
- **Drone 2 (D2):** Carries a high-resolution camera streaming video through D1 via the mesh network. Video frames are sent through the 5G uplink to the edge analytics node.
- **Drone 3 (D3):** Optionally deployed to expand the surveillance radius, also using BATMAN-based multi-hop connectivity.

All drones run lightweight BATMAN routing software to ensure reliable mesh formation and self-healing connectivity between nodes.

3) *Edge Computing and AI Analytics:* A dedicated edge device (Nvidia Jetson Orin Nano) hosts the custom model for human detection based on UWS-YOLO architecture for real-time human intrusion detection. The edge AI pipeline processes live video feeds received from the drone with an average inference latency below 25 ms. Detected events are visualised on a Grafana dashboard in near real-time.

C. Monitoring and Slicing Orchestration

Grafana and Timescale DB are used to log and visualise network metrics such as throughput, jitter, and latency. A dedicated monitoring xApp provides RESTful APIs to extract radio and QoS statistics from the FlexRIC interface. A slicing xApp dynamically enforces low-latency QoS profiles (URLLC-type) for drone video feeds and standard eMBB slices for training content.

D. Test Scenarios

The experiments were executed in three stages:

Fig. 3: DCIC 5G Private Network testbed setup used for the aerospace surveillance demonstration. The image shows the Lite-On FlexiFI O-RU antennas connected to the BubbleRAN MX-PDK compute cluster, autonomous drones equipped with Raspberry Pi controllers, cameras and 5G Quectel modules.

- 1) **Normal Operation:** Baseline network with minimal traffic, capturing latency and throughput benchmarks.
- 2) **Congestion Simulation:** iPerf-based traffic injection to saturate bandwidth, testing video stability under load.
- 3) **Slicing Activation:** Re-allocation of resources via xApp to prioritise the URLLC slice for the drone video stream.

Metrics collected include round-trip latency, packet loss, throughput, and end-to-end detection delay between drone video capture and AI alert generation.

V. RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Baseline vs. Congested Conditions

Results show that during congestion, average end-to-end latency for the drone video stream increased from 12 ms to 85 ms, as shown in Fig. 4 Upon activating the URLLC slice, latency reduced to under 15 ms with zero packet loss.

B. Mesh Network Resilience

To evaluate the performance of the BATMAN-ADV-based MESH network, transmission tests were conducted using the *iPerf* tool among four drones equipped with Raspberry Pi 5 modules. The objective was to analyze how the effective bandwidth varied as the number of hops increased within the MESH topology.

The obtained results are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I: Measured bandwidth with iPerf in multi-hop MESH configuration

Number of Hops	Bandwidth (Mbps)
1 (2 drones)	116.26
2 (3 drones)	49.24
3 (4 drones)	22.32

As expected, the available bandwidth decreases progressively as the number of hops increases. This behavior is typical in MESH networks, since each intermediate node must receive and retransmit the data, introducing latency and dividing the overall channel capacity among multiple links.

In this implementation, the reduction in performance is mainly attributed to the limitations of the integrated WiFi interface on the Raspberry Pi 5. Although the device supports high theoretical data rates, its performance in ad-hoc mode is constrained by internal processing overhead, half-duplex operation, and the additional routing traffic handled by the BATMAN-ADV protocol.

Consequently, each additional hop introduces both retransmission overhead and lower effective throughput. This effect becomes especially relevant in data-intensive transmissions, such as real-time video streaming, where the processing capacity and wireless efficiency of each node directly impact overall network performance.

Fig. 5 illustrates the measured bandwidth trend as a function of the number of hops.

These results confirm the expected degradation in bandwidth as the number of hops increases, highlighting the influence of the Raspberry Pi 5's wireless interface and processing capacity on the multi-hop data transmission performance.

C. Edge AI Inference Performance

The human detector model achieved a detection latency of 23 ms per frame, sustaining 25 FPS with 95% detection accuracy in the test scenario.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper has presented the design, deployment, and evaluation of a 5G-enabled Private Network integrating UAV-based

Fig. 4: Experimental results of AR/VR training and surveillance UAV video streaming under varying network conditions, demonstrating how 5G network slicing ensures reliable performance and service continuity for mission-critical aerospace operations.

Fig. 5: Measured bandwidth as a function of the number of hops in the MESH network.

surveillance, edge computing, and intelligent network slicing for aerospace operations. The experimental results demonstrate that the convergence of private 5G infrastructure, mesh networking, and edge AI can effectively support mission-critical applications requiring low latency, reliability, and scalability. Specifically, network slicing ensured predictable performance under congestion, while the BATMAN-ADV mesh protocol provided resilient connectivity across distributed UAVs.

Several practical insights were gained through the implementation. First, end-to-end latency was primarily influenced by edge inference time and uplink congestion, underscoring the importance of adaptive resource management. Second, xApp-driven automation proved valuable for enforcing Quality-of-Service (QoS) guarantees dynamically. Third, BATMAN-ADV demonstrated a lightweight and flexible solution for UAV swarms, simplifying ad-hoc deployment without centralised control. Beyond technical metrics, the demonstrator also addressed regional challenges identified in previous 5G adoption studies, offering tangible evidence of how private 5G networks can drive industrial digital transformation.

Future work will focus on extending the system towards predictive maintenance and real-time asset management within aerospace environments. Further research will explore multi-slice orchestration and AI-assisted network management through Dynamic Network Slicing, enabling the system to autonomously adapt to contextual factors such as network load, UAV density, and operational priority. These advancements aim to strengthen the role of 5G Private Networks as a foun-

dational technology for autonomous industrial ecosystems.

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